

STIFFENED COMPOSITE PARTS BY RESIN INFUSION PROCESS FOR AIRCRAFT APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

Composite structural design and manufacturing using “Resin Infusion” process were studied in order to catch both of product reliability and cost reduction following the industrial requirements. Carbon fibers were spreading and modified to non-clamed fabric (NCF) and high Tg epoxy resin were formulated under the concerning of fabrication process. Aircraft’s landing gear door was selected as prototype to evaluate the material and manufacturing process in this study. Aluminum structured door was converted to sandwich composite design and analysis assisted to optimize the balance between weight reduction and structural stiffness. Final product was compared with original product in both weight and cost reduction.

1 INTRODUCTION

Pre-impregnated Carbon fiber curing by autoclave is the representative composite manufacturing process of aircraft structure and major aircraft manufacturers are applied to their main products, like Boeing 787 series and Airbus 320 line. The incidental expense like facilities and maintenance for this manufacturing system, however, is required to reduce the cost and improve the efficiency of production.

The various composite material and manufacturing process were had been studied by school and companies in order to have cost comparatives over other metal materials taking the advantaged of weight reduction. Pre-preg materials were modified and developed for curing without pressure, in other words, OOA (Out of Autoclave) to make reduce the production cost. The defects’ standard of aircraft composite parts was high and difficult to meet quality requirement.

Thermoplastic materials were concerned as alternatives of structural composite. The high forming temperature and lower properties of matrix compared with epoxy matrix would take time to replace the pre-preg/autoclave. The thermoplastic materials are under development to enhance their function and started to replace small aluminum parts with lower cost production.

All over the efforts of development of reducing the cost, the material suppliers were started to produce the resin and fiber for resin transfer molding or resin infusion. Resin with high glass transition temperature has low enough viscosity to infuse over the aircraft parts at proper temperature and the carbon fabric were coated to make layup easier. The worthiness of RI (Resin Infusion) or RTM(Resin Transfer Molding) is able to deign composite parts simple like one-piece without assembly. Sandwich composite is able to expand the size and large one-piece sandwich structure without additional boding or fastening is available. Task of large-scale of initial investment for facilities or maintenance for production rather than autoclave will not be involved to companies.

Resin infusion is the broad meaning of resin infusion process of composite Laminated dry mat on the mold were sealed in vacuum and liquid resin flows through the all over the mold with vacuum assist or injection pressure. The mold could be the closed rigid mold or one-side rigid with vacuum

pressure bagging on the other side. Over the prepreg/autoclave parts, the resin contents were measured in 3~4 % higher than the prepreg/autoclave parts, which results the thickness increased with same structure. In spite of limit of high volume ratio resin of RI composite, large scale of one piece of composite design is available. It is from the difficulties of precise control of the resin flow rate and raw material properties are enough to stable. In this project, metal-based design structure of aircraft parts are converted to composite design, which is stiffened structure with complex configured sandwich core and laminate with metal parts hinge assembly. The raw resin and carbon CNF were developed to optimize in design and manufacturing process is defined.

2 STRUCTURAL DESIGN FROM METAL TO COMPOSITE

Aluminum designed main landing gear (MLG) door is selected to a target of this manufacturing method research. This complex figured stiffened panel parts by interface is good to take the advantage of RI method of composite manufacturing with same performance with light weight.

Figure 1 Aluminum structured landing gear door for aircraft

In order to maintain the interface, hinge point and geometry were remained with metal design. The original design is consist of two thin forming aluminum sheet and it also should be a geometry constrained. Because of following the interface of inner and outer of door, the sandwich contour was defined. The hinge fitting to composite were designed in laminate to overcome the bearing strength. Foam core configuration was complex and results the complex of upper skin layup. Structural analysis were following after design and optimized the stacking sequence

Figure 2 Metal designed door converted to composite structured design

3 MATERIAL & MANUFACTURING PROCESS

3.1 Materials

Carbon fiber reinforcement is the reasonable replacement of aluminum structure while the identical performance with light weight should running. The Non-clamped fabrics (NCF) were applied to this research to perform the stiffness rather than carbon fabric. The initial structural analysis supports the basic sequence definition. Production of basic NCF sequence is directly corresponding to the labor cost producing composite parts. Two type of $[+45^\circ/-45^\circ]$ and $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ were defined and produced in this research. Single layer of NCF has $120\sim 150\text{g/cm}^3$ of aerial weight and two-layer of NCF were fabricated in 280 g/cm^3 of aerial weight.

Figure 3 NCF Production and Carbon NCF with 280 g/cm^3 of aerial weight

Epoxy based resin were formulated with curing agent and hardener. Glass transition temperature (T_g) is required in higher than 350°F and blended resin needs enough working time to inject the resin into the large and complex parts to keep the stable curing process. The resin, at the final stage of research, were blended and injected at temperature of 80°C . Curing cycle defined concerning DCS results and production rate.

Figure 4 Formulated Resin Viscosity

Resin film using same materials with bulk resin were fabricated for this project. Resin Infusion of sandwich composite is hard to make resin flow parallel between upper and bottom skin and this is easily caused of void-trapping and de-bonding between skin and core. The resin film makes bottom skin soak enough into the resin and avoid the void. In order to improve the resin flow in the interface of skin and core, core is machined to make the small road, slot on the surface.

Figure 5 Resin Film casting

Polymethacrylimide (PMI) core with 110 g/cm^3 of density was machined by CNC since it stands at high curing temperature of aircraft composites (350°F). Large block of foam core were machined by CNC due to the complex configured modeling by assembly interface.

3.2 Carbon NCF Preforming & Layup

Since the carbon dry NCF was hard to maintain their own shape during layup not like pre-preg, dry mat preforming process added. Co-polyamide binder was applied to one-side surface of dry-mat and laid up in preformed mold with vacuum bag. The additional storage in the oven at certain temperature, the binder materials had gone and the preformed shape is maintained. Three or four layers were preformed at once and each of layers was modified by cutting and draping in order to avoid the bridge effect.

Figure 6 As-received NCF layup and preforming NCF layup

NCF mat and resin film were laid-up on the mold following the laser projection program defined by modified modelling. After PMI foam core were placed in the middle of layup process, the complex and preformed NCF were laid-up over core. The each steps of compaction will help align of reinforcement and to avoid the bridge effects on foam core. Double vacuum bagging was sealed the composite package with the layup mold and it is finally ready to cure.

3.3 Resin Infusion

Formulated resin was preheated in the oven to reduce the viscosity. Preheated resin were injected in to the vacuum bag in preheated mold at 100°C . The resin injection was monitored and additional injection force but vacuum was not applied to enough soaking time and flow rate. After resin injection completed, resin inlet were closed and keep the mold and vacuum bag in the oven.

Figure 7 Resin injection flow rate, from upper right to left side; 0, 5 and 13min after injection, from lower right to left side; 24, 35 and 40min

3.4 Curing

Resin-Infused double-vacuum bag was cured in 180°C oven for 2 hours after holding for 4 hours at 120°C. Thermocouples attached on the mold and parts and it was able to control the curing temperature. The product were release from the mold below 50°C of temperature.

Figure 8 Cure cycle chart

4 RESULTS AND QUALIFICATION

4.1 General Inspection

The composite product was inspected to evaluate the quality of product. Dimension were inspected with 3D scanning and compared with modelling. Since the curved geometry designed with concerning the coupling of extensional and bending, change of products' curvature was concerned with thermal expansion of mold and parts. The 3D scan results showed that modified mold design concerning thermal expansion was working well; the gap between model and product were from 0.07~1.42mm. The lowest area of curvature was almost to fit to the model and the edges of door were 1.42mm at most. Another general inspection of composite parts is non-destructive test and the A-scan were performed and no defect or error were detected at the 6DB attenuation.

Figure 9 Geometry inspection with 3D scanning, the difference between model and product; yellow denote 0.07mm and light blue does 1.42mm

Figure 10 RI composite MLG Door after full Assembly, ready for installation to the aircraft

4.2 Weight and Cost Reduction

After all inspection from the quality inception, the door was placed on the balance. Weight was 3% difference with design and the 23% of reduction from the aluminium door. Though the additional structural test should support to this result, the composite optimized design could save the weight.

The cost of carbon-fiber-composite door is estimated for comparing with autoclave curing parts, 22% cost reduction referred from lower cost of raw-materials (pre-preg vs. dry-mat & resin) and less man-hour. The material maintenance and the facilities will make the difference large under the serial and mass production.

In addition to weight reduction from aluminium structure, cost were remained and the weight reduction form the aluminium structure paid nothing for it

5 CONCLUSION

This paper presented the new process of OOA composite structure manufacturing process using Resin Infusion with Carbon NCF concerning the mass production. Resin Infusion composite manufacturing process was reduced both of the weight over aluminum and the cost over pre-preg composite. The structural design concerning manufacturing process will give a chance to reduce the material and labor cost. This whole process could expand not only autoclave cured composite structure alternatives in aircraft, but also the defense and automotive parts of cost competition.

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